

THEORETICAL ASPECTS AND CONCEPTUAL APPROACHES TO UNDERSTANDING THE CULTURE OF READING.

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Abstract

In this article, the author analyzes the main approaches to defining the culture of reading, its structural elements, functions and significance in modern society. The influence of various factors, such as the educational environment, digital technologies and socio-cultural traditions, on the formation and development of reading culture is studied. The author pays special attention to the skills of critical understanding of the text, information literacy and the role of reading in the intellectual and spiritual development of the individual.

Аннотация

В данной статье автор исследует основные подходы к определению культуры чтения, её структурные элементы, функции и значение в современном обществе. Анализирует влияние различных факторов, таких как образовательная среда, цифровые технологии и социокультурные традиции, на формирование и развитие читательской культуры. Особое внимание автор уделяет навыкам критического осмысления текста, информационной грамотности и роли чтения в интеллектуальном и духовном развитии личности.

Key words: reading culture, youth, crisis of reading culture, components of reading culture, electronic publications, book culture. youth leisure

Ключевые слова: культура чтения, молодежь, кризис читательской культуры, компоненты читательской культуры, электронные издания, досуг молодежи.

Introduction

The analysis of scientific works of domestic and foreign researchers on this topic indicates the need to revise the existing approaches to the study of reading culture and education of young people in Uzbekistan. The development of effective measures for the formation of reading culture is possible, firstly, on the basis of interdisciplinary research (philosophy, sociology, pedagogy) and, secondly, by combining the efforts of various social groups, including scientists, teachers, public figures and parents.

Over the past 10-15 years, changes in educational, socio-cultural and economic spheres have led to a change in the attitude of young people both to culture in general and to reading books. In the scientific and cultural community this situation has been called the 'crisis of reading culture'. The appeal to the analysis of young people's perception of the reading process is due to the fact that at the end of XX - beginning of XXI century under the influence of social, economic, political and cultural changes there is a situation that requires not only its study from the standpoint of such sciences as philosophy, cultural studies, history, psychology, pedagogy, physiology and computer science, but also the assessment of possible negative consequences for society, their prevention and, if possible, their elimination.

V. Borodina adheres to a similar point of view, noting that the solution to this problem requires a holistic approach at the interdisciplinary level. The acute need to analyse and systematize heterogeneous interdisciplinary knowledge about reading necessitates the synthesis of scientific ideas about its various aspects on a new theoretical and methodological basis, which is determined by a number of factors. [1]

E. Melnikova and A. Kirichek note that the results of studies of various aspects of reading, based on empirical and theoretical data, remain fragmented, unsystematised and not united into a single whole. [2;3]

Main part

The topic of reading in the modern world has become acute and controversial, requiring an objective and impartial analysis. Firstly, it is obvious that the leisure time of young people has changed significantly, and secondly, it is becoming increasingly clear that the assessment of the current state of reading culture is impossible using previously applied methodological approaches. A comprehensive analysis using modern research methods is necessary for a full understanding of modern reading.

Y. Melentieva, relying on Epictetus' idea that philosophising begins with the realisation of one's own powerlessness, emphasises the lack of deep philosophical reflection on modern processes in the sphere of reading. She notes that the lack of a philosophical view and methodological grounding negatively affects scientific approaches to the study of reading within other disciplines. [4]

The results of research conducted by specialists in the field of reading over the last fifteen to twenty years have highlighted the following trend that confirms our thought:

- attitudes towards reading have changed – reading has become pragmatic and utilitarian;
- reading time in free time has decreased;
- readers still prefer mass and entertainment reading;
- electronic media are far ahead of the reader's preference for paper products;
- cultural, educational, aesthetic reading is becoming an elitist pastime. [5]

It is important to emphasise that the concept of 'reading culture' includes several key components that form its multifaceted essence. These include culture in general, the history of the emergence and development of the book (book culture), the reading process itself, the level of reading literacy, writing, as well as the reader's personality. The study of these elements makes it possible to comprehensively and deeply investigate the phenomenon of reading culture.

B. Vasiliev, considering the book as a source of culture, states that book culture is an integral and significant part of both domestic and world cultural heritage. In the scientific environment it is presented as a multilevel model, which in this case acts in the form of a triune system: a) the sphere of material production (book production), b) the culture of consumption of book products and c) the field of spiritual creativity and intellectual development. [6]

One of the key elements of reading culture is the reading process itself, which is a complex sociocultural phenomenon. Reading is studied within the framework of various scientific disciplines, including literary studies, philosophy, cultural studies, psychology and pedagogy. It contributes to the intellectual development of a person, enriches his knowledge, expands the boundaries of personal experience, helps to master the values of world culture and forms cultural competence, contributing to social adaptation.

Reading not only preserves and transmits the intellectual heritage of society, ensuring the continuity of knowledge and skills, but also serves as a tool for learning about the world, forming moral and spiritual guidelines, training and education. This intellectual and cognitive process plays a crucial role in the development of personality and is an integral element in the formation of intellectual culture, contributing to the formation of a highly developed, humane and spiritual and moral society.

N. Svetlovskaya states that: 'Reading is practically the only reliable way of 'humanisation', as it allows to expand the child's circle of communication limited by real life and, helping him, looking, as in a mirror, into the 'alien' experience,

passing the school of mastering 'alien' speech – thoughts, feelings, evaluations – to search and find himself and his place in life.' [7]

Technological innovations make their adjustments in people's lives, and inevitably there is a new format of reading – electronic (screen) reading, which today becomes one of the most popular and convenient ways of perceiving information. However, the printed book does not lose its importance, continuing to co-exist with digital formats, just as in the Gutenberg era handwritten books co-existed with printed editions for some time. For the moment, they complement each other, not exclude each other.

Reading culture is a complex, dynamic and multifaceted phenomenon that shapes both the individual and society as a whole. It is determined by spiritual and cognitive needs that contribute to the transformation of an individual into a personality. The reading culture of young people is manifested in their reading experience, value attitude to books and level of reading competence.

Thus, reading culture encompasses not only the individual's personal qualities (especially spiritual qualities), but also the influence of society, age characteristics and aspirations. It presupposes a conscious and serious attitude to the reading process, because true reading – whether paper or e-book – is capable of transforming a person.

Reading plays an important role in a person's life, especially a young person, but it is not an end in itself. It is primarily a tool that serves two main purposes: the acquisition of knowledge and the formation of moral values. According to the philosopher-stoic Epictetus: 'Reading a book is not a deed, but preparation for a deed. When there is a case to help a person, it should not hesitate to postpone reading even the most good and useful book. Reading a book should not be for yourself, but for the service of people, for further application of what you read in life.' [8]

'Man is integral, he embodies, personifies in himself the richness of social relations, connections, the entire available level of culture. All the needs, interests, goals of society live, function not in some independent life of their own, they are somehow, whether directly or indirectly, expressed, embodied in the needs, interests, goals, etc. of each particular individual, personality, person. Man, thus, carries in himself a whole social cosmos', – writes philosopher V.Barulin. [9]

Man's comprehension of himself, society as a part of nature and this world is carried out in various types: philosophical, scientific, religious, historical. The set of such cognitive types at different stages of human development in different

civilisations and cultures is diverse and different. Each type of cognition has its own special features, specificity, distinguishing it from other types.

One of such means of cognition of the world, linking man with society, nature and other (similar) subjects is his reading culture.

Conclusion

The analysis of reading culture as one of the forms of influence on the worldview, behaviour and spiritual image of young people allows us to draw a number of important conclusions and findings. First of all, in the process of research it was established that reading culture since ancient times has been not only the main indicator of the level of culture of society, but also an integral condition for its development. With the formation and development of reading culture as a substructure of the general culture of man, morality, spirituality of people, their relations to each other, to the environment, values change, and society itself develops.

On the other hand, the rapidly changing world, dynamic development of information culture and society, new economic and socio-cultural changes make their own adjustments in the value orientations and life preferences of young readers. Intensive development of electronic technologies and interactive network space has increased the number of electronic publications, caused the emergence of digital libraries, virtual book clubs, network communities, and numerous websites. And, as a result, the reader's attitude to traditional books has changed. This is not to say that mankind has stopped reading. No. It's just that the reader has moved to another, new, information-technological level. He still remains Homo Legens, the Reading Man, but, as it seems to us, with the addition of electronus – Homo legens electronus.

Promotion of reading to the masses, to the people, formation of high reading culture is the main factor of formation of morality and spirituality of youth, harmoniously developed personality capable of creative, productive and independent orientation in the rapidly developing information society. And until this issue is not fully resolved, it will constantly meet us in life as an obstacle.

References:

1. Borodina V.E. Reader's development of personality: theoretical and methodological aspects. // Abstract of the dissertation... Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences. St. Petersburg, 2007, - P. 2
2. Melnikova E. Imaginary book / Essays on the history of folklore about books and reading in Russia. - St. Petersburg: Publishing house of the European University in St. Petersburg, 2011. -C. 19-33

3. Kirichek A.S. Culture of reading as a subject of cognition. / Scientific Notes of the V.I. Vernadsky Tauride National University // Series 'Problems of pedagogy of secondary and higher schools'. Vol. 27 (66). 2014 г. № 3. - C. 35-46.]
4. Melentieva Y.P. General theory of reading, -M.: Nauka. 2015. - C. 133
5. Galaktionova T.G. Librarianship / article Reading of schoolchildren as a socio-pedagogical phenomenon of open education: research problems. -M. 2006. - C. 71
6. Vasiliev V.I. //Book as a source of culture: problems and methods of research : proceedings of the international scientific conference. - M.: Nauka, 2008. - C. 381-399
7. Svetlovskaya N.N. Methodical bases of formation of 'talented reader'. - Yaroslavl. 2004, -C. 45
8. Epictetus. What is our good? Selected thoughts of the Roman sage. URL: <http://www.sky-art.com/epictet/blago/blago00.htm>.
9. Barulin V.S. Social Philosophy: Textbook. - Ed. 2nd. - M.: FAIRE-PRESS, 2000. - C. 25

